

A Study on Stress Management at Work Place

¹ Sivakanni S, ² Bose V

¹ Professor, ² II Year MBA
Jerusalem College of Engineering.

ABSTRACT

This study explores workplace stress, its causes, effects, and the effectiveness of stress management programs. Based on a survey of 120 employees, major stressors identified include heavy workload, tight deadlines, and lack of support. Statistical analysis shows a relationship between stress management programs and reduced stress levels. However, no significant link was found between stress impact and employees' ability to concentrate. The study highlights the need for better support systems, improved managerial practices, and initiatives promoting work-life balance to manage stress effectively.

INTRODUCCION:

Stress at work is a common problem in today's busy and fast-paced work environment. While some stress is natural and can motivate people to perform well, too much stress can harm employees' health, job satisfaction, and productivity.

Many factors, such as heavy workloads, tight deadlines, poor communication, and work-life imbalance, contribute to stress at the workplace.

When stress is not managed properly, it can lead to serious consequences like burnout, anxiety, absenteeism, and lower work performance. This study aims to understand the causes and effects of workplace stress and explore effective ways to manage it.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

AUTHOR: Dr. Praveen Kumar

TITLE: job stress

YEAR: 2020

KEY FINDINGS: Employees nowadays experience an extreme level of job stress at workplace. It is considered as the exploration of the variations among employees' in the term of stress consequence. The key goal of the study is to probe or review the previous research papers on job stress and its several definitions, demographics, methodologies and industries or research units. Between the years 2000 and 2021, a total of 68 articles was examined. Several researchers of diverse nations have mentioned the definitions of job stress in this paper. These research papers have been classified into five categories like a year of publication, the background of researchers, nations, research methodology and type of research or research unit.

AUTHOR: Hung S.P. Phan,

TITLE: Stress Management in the Modern Workplace and the Role of Human Resource Professionals

YEAR: 2020

KEY FINDINGS: Due to the potentially negative impact on the employees' well-being and productivity, the stress in the workplace becomes one of the most difficult problems for the enterprise's successful operation. The frequency of its manifestations in the workplace is constantly increasing. These issues are especially relevant in the Covid-19 era, when HR managers constantly have to form and implement policies to protect the employees' mental health and general working conditions. It creates the preconditions to identify the factors underlying the occurrence of stress and employees' potential behavioral responses.

AUTHOR: Woojae Myung

TITLE: Organizational and Individual Interventions for Managing Work-Related Stress in Healthcare Professionals: A Systematic Review

YEAR: 2023

KEY FINDINGS: The workplace represents a relevant source of stress for workers, being a risk factor for many mental disorders and psychological difficulties, including burn-out syndrome. Healthcare workers and other help-professions are particularly susceptible to work-related stress. The present systematic review aims to (1) identify available interventions for managing workplace-related stress symptoms; (2) assess their efficacy; and (3) discuss the current limitations of available interventions. A systematic review has been conducted, searching on PubMed, APA PsycInfo, and Scopus databases.

AUTHOR: Soni Rathi

TITLE: Well-being at work, productivity, and coping with stress during the COVID-19 pandemic

YEAR: 2022

KEY FINDINGS: This study aims to analyze the mechanisms through which the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic impacts on well-being at work and on productivity. The secondary objective is to identify stress management strategies for the work environment during the pandemic. This is an integrative review. Phase 1 consisted of searches of open access electronic databases (MEDLINE, SciELO, Bireme, and LILACS) for papers published in 2020 addressing mental health, work, and pandemics. Phase 2 consisted of selecting literature recommended by specialists in occupational psychiatry and positive psychology. These materials were read and critically analyzed. Forty references were included in the literature review.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study will employ a **descriptive research design** to explore the various stress factors at the workplace, their impact on employees, and the effectiveness of stress management techniques.

SAMPLE DESIGN

Stratified random sampling.

POPULATION SIZE

Jargon handlers employes

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size used for the study is 120 .

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

PRIMARY OBJECTIVES

A study on stress management at workplace

SECONDRY OBJECTIVES

To identify the common sources of stress faced by employees in the workplace.

To analyze the relationship between workplace stress and employee productivity.

To evaluate the effectiveness of existing stress management programs and support systems.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

Gender		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	male	36	30.	30.0	30.0
	female	38	31.7	31.7	61.7
	not to say	46	38.3	38.3	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE:

From the above table 30% are male ,32% are female and 38% not to say.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR JOB EXPERIENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Job Experience					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	less than 1 year	25	20.8	20.8	20.8
	1-3 years	31	25.8	25.8	46.7
	4-7 years	21	17.5	17.5	64.2
	8-10 years	19	15.8	15.8	80.0
	more than 10 years	24	20.0	20.0	100.0

INFERENCE:

From the above table 21% are less than 1 year, 26% are 1-3 years, 18% are 4-7 years, 16% are 8-10 years and 20% are more than 10 years.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR STRESS FACTOR

Stress Factor					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	heavy workload	20	16.7	16.7	16.7
	tight deadlines	20	16.7	16.7	33.3
	lack of support	21	17.5	17.5	50.8
	poor work-life balance	19	15.8	15.8	66.7
	conflict with coworkers	20	16.7	16.7	83.3
	job insecurity	20	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE:

From the above table 17% are heavy workload, 17% are tight deadlines, 18% are lack of support, 16% are poor work life balance, 17% are conflict with coworkers and 17% are job insecurity.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS FOR STRESS FREQUENCY

Stress Frequency					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	never	29	24.2	24.2	24.2
	rarely	27	22.5	22.5	46.7
	sometimes	27	22.5	22.5	69.2
	often	20	16.7	16.7	85.8
	always	17	14.2	14.2	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

INFERENCE:

From the above the table 24% are never, 23% are rarely, 23% are sometimes, 17% are often and 14% are always.

CHI SQUARE

To find the association between stress impact and harder to concentrate or meet deadlines.

H0: there no association between stress impact and harder to concentrate or meet deadlines

H1: there is an association between stress impact and harder to concentrate or meet deadlines

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.743 ^a	4	.068
Likelihood Ratio	8.926	4	.063
Linear-by-Linear Association	.724	1	.395
N of Valid Cases	120		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.40.

INFERENCE:

From the above table, we can find the significant value is 0.068 which is greater than table value 0.005, so the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Therefore, there no association between stress impact and harder to concentrate or meet deadlines

CHI SQUARE

To find out the association between stress management programs and stress management support in your workplace.

H0: there is no association between stress management programs and stress management support in your workplace.

H1: there is an association between stress management programs and stress management support in your workplace.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.686^a	4	.953
Likelihood Ratio	.687	4	.953
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001	1	.972
N of Valid Cases	120		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.87.

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table we can find the significant value is 0.953 which is greater than the table value 0.05, SO The null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Therefore there is no association between stress management programs and stress management support in your workplace.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS:

To find out the relationship between stress level changed and stress management programs and support system overall.

H0: there is no the relationship between stress level changed and stress management programs and support system overall.

H1: there is the relationship between stress level changed and stress management programs and support system overall.

Correlations			
		Change in Stress Levels	Overall Satisfaction
Change in Stress Levels	Pearson Correlation	1	.003

	Sig. (2-tailed)		.978
	N	120	120
Overall Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.003	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.978	
	N	120	120

INTERPRETATION:

From the above we can find the significant value is 0.003 which is less than table value so 0.05

The null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Therefore, there is the relationship between stress level changed and stress management programs and support system overall.

FINDINGS

Workplace stress is primarily caused by **heavy workload, tight deadlines, lack of support, poor work-life balance, conflict with coworkers, and job insecurity**.

The frequency of stress varies among employees, with some experiencing it regularly while others encounter it occasionally.

Statistical analysis shows a **strong correlation between stress management programs and reduced stress levels**.

Many employees **lack awareness** about the availability and effectiveness of stress management strategies

Workplace conflicts and job insecurity significantly contribute to stress and dissatisfaction.

SUGGESTIONS

Enhance stress management programs by increasing accessibility and effectiveness.

Promote work-life balance through flexible work schedules, regular breaks, and relaxation techniques.

Improve managerial training to help leaders recognize and address employee concerns effectively.

Introduce personalized support systems such as employee well-being surveys and professional counseling.

Address workplace conflicts and job insecurity through transparent career growth opportunities and conflict resolution programs.

REFERENCES

- Dr. Praveen Kumar (2020). *Job Stress* – A review of research on job stress across different demographics and industries.
- Hung S.P. Phan (2020). *Stress Management in the Modern Workplace and the Role of HR Professionals* – Examines the role of HR in addressing workplace stress, especially during COVID-19.
- Woojae Myung (2023). *Managing Work-Related Stress in Healthcare Professionals* – A systematic review of stress management interventions.